

SPAN

SAPROXYLIC HABITAT NETWORK

**Design of electric fences in the Cansiglio forest (FVG)
for the LIFE SPAN project**

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Muzzini V.G.¹, De Cinti B.¹, Sicuriello F.¹, Latilla L.¹, Di Salvatore U.², Lazzerini G.³, Ferretti F.³,

1 - CNR - Institute of Research on Terrestrial Ecosystems, Strada Provinciale 35d, km. 0,700, Montelibretti - Rome (Italy)

2 - CREA Research Centre for Politics and Bioeconomy, Via Lombardia 7, I-65012 Cepagatti, PE, Italy

3 - CREA Research Centre for Forestry and Wood, Viale S. Margherita 80, I-52100 Arezzo, Italy

Introduction

The European LIFE SPAN (Saproxylic Habitat Network) project aims to develop and test management solutions which, by integrating with the models already implemented in protected areas and productive forests, guarantee the protection of forest biodiversity. In particular, the aim is to create, within the forest, a network of "Senescence areas (SHS - Saproxylic Habitat Sites)" to encourage the movement and dispersion of the various saproxylic species through the surrounding areas, ensuring the protection of the forest biodiversity, with particular attention to saproxylic biodiversity.

The European sites included in the project and chosen for the creation of the SHS are the Eastern Cansiglio forest in Italy (Fruli Venezia Giulia - 46.079444 North, 12.415 East) and the Sailershausen forest located in Bavaria, near Würzburg (50.0601397 North, 10.4476414 East - Fig.1).

Fig.1 – Location of the Cansiglio Forest and the Sailershausen Forest

Within the forests, in specially selected areas, interventions will be implemented to increase the presence of dead wood, microhabitats, structural heterogeneity and clearings. The interventions will be carried out in 25 points of the Italian demonstration area, and in 18 of the German one.

The project envisaged the creation of clearings of about 1500 square meters, within the SHSs, to increase the diversity of herbaceous species and the quantity of dead wood exposed to the sun.

According to what is reported in the Forest Management Plan of the Eastern Cansiglio Regional Forest, the most recent estimates quantify the deer population in the entire Cansiglio area at around 3000 individuals. The excessive load of ungulate fauna constitutes a disturbing factor in fact the action of the deer towards the forest is essentially manifested by repeated browsing at the vegetative apexes with

serious effects on growth which can lead to a drastic reduction in renewal up to, in the most striking cases, cancel it completely.

The open areas will then be enclosed with fences using some of the woody material obtained from the interventions, to prevent the attendance of animals, especially ungulates, from creating problems for natural regeneration.

The objective of this document is therefore to describe the technical solutions used for the creation of the electric fence of the clearings.

Clearing area (GAP)

The clearings created in the SHSs are one for each area, therefore for the Cansiglio Forest, a total of 25. Not all clearings will be electrified, but the fence will be created only on 18 GAPs (Tab.1) leaving wood cut on the ground on the remaining ones. The size of the clearing is approximately 44 m in diameter for a total surface area of approximately 1500 m².

The SHSs are located in most cases on the north-west facing side of the forest, therefore little exposed to direct sunlight, and are also inclined with variable slopes depending on the topography of the area (Fig.2 and 3).

Table 1 – SHS with electric fences

SHS – Electric Fence
12D
14B (14F)
11C
10C
10E
15C
16B
16F
9A
9B
8B
17E
17G
17F
18D
19F
Caneva4
Budoia1

Fig. 2 – Photo of a clearing

FORESTA REGIONALE DEL CANSIGLIO
COROGRAFIA SCALA 1/20000

Legenda

 AREA SHS FR CANSIGLIO (con numero di p.lla)

Fig. 3 – Topography with SHSs

Electric Fence

The fence has a diameter of about 50 m in order to surround the clearing in the undergrowth part and have fewer problems with the growth of herbaceous vegetation. There are 6 electrical wires surrounding the area, spaced 20 cm apart, with the first 40 cm away from the ground (Fig.4). A pole is placed every ten meters along the circumference to support the insulators (Fig.5). Table 2 shows some overall measures of the project.

The fence is made up of the components described in table 3. The main problem is constituted by the electric consumption of the electrification device which must necessarily be fed continuously for 24 hours a day, for the entire growing season. The solution we chose to adopt involves the use of photovoltaic panels coupled with a rechargeable battery.

Fig. 4 – Wooden pole with insulators and wires

Fig. 5 – Electric Fence

Table 2 – Dimensional characteristics of the Electric Fence Project

Features x GAP	
radius (m)	30
circumference (m)	188.5
N of wires	6
Length (m)	1131
N of poles	19
n electrical insulators	114

In total, the project includes for 18 fences, 20 km of electric wire, 340 poles and 2060 electric insulators.

Table 3 – Electric Fence Equipment

Equipment	
Electrifier	Danger signals
Control unit monitoring	Gate handle
Monitoring sensor	Chestnut poles D 8 cm
Insulators	Chestnut poles D 10/12 cm
Electrical tape	Electric wire
LiFePO412V 50Ah battery	Strapping machine
Photovoltaic Panel 100W 12V	Strap
metal box	Strap seals
box support pole 415 mm	accessories

The equipment described in table 3 has a total cost of approximately 30000 euros.

Electrifier

The electrical characteristics chosen to electrify the fence are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 – Technical specifications

Technical specifications of the Electrifier	
Source of energy	12 Volt/ 230 Volt
Accumulated energy	7.6 joule
Energy output	5 Joule
Voltage at 500 Ohm	7.200 Volt
Open circuit voltage	10.000 Volt
Energy Consumption	133-430 mA
Recommended number of ground rods	3 Pz. Art.Nr. 44375
Number of connectable networks	18 Pz.
Dimensions W x H x D mm	290 x 210 x 115
Product type	Electrifier 12V
Animals	Sheep / Wolf / Horse Boar / Deer / Galloway Pork / Beef /Pony Goat / Roe Deer

Power to the system

The power supply is supplied by a 12 V battery. The power supply should be active all year round, but in winter it snows heavily in the Cansiglio forest consequently the fence as thought could be subject to a short circuit with deep snow.

Due to the characteristics of the forest environment, a lithium ion battery was chosen with a protection device against overcharging and deep discharge which could irreparably damage the battery.

To recharge the battery it was decided to use two 100 W photovoltaic panels for each power system since due to the shape of the clearing, surrounded by trees approximately 20 meters high, direct sunlight should be available for relatively few hours per day during the summer season. A double panel was therefore hypothesized, facing south and positioned to the north-east and north-west of the clearing, oriented towards the centre of the clearing (Fig.6).

Fig. 6 – Inclined clearing with arrangement of photovoltaic panels in blue and energizer in purple.

Inclination of the photovoltaic panel with respect to the horizontal

It is important to position the photovoltaic panel with the best possible inclination (which in our latitudes is between 30 and 35 degrees). The further you go towards the poles of the globe, the more vertical the panels will have to be. In Italy the optimal inclination is 30-35 degrees compared to the horizontal. Below is the formula to identify the best inclination based on latitude for Italy range:

$$\text{Optimal inclination} = \text{Latitude} \quad [1]$$

Optimal inclination at the Cansiglio Forest = $46.06 = 46^\circ$

In the case of uneven terrain, the relative slope with respect to the horizontal must be taken into account.

Remote monitoring

The electric fences will be monitored remotely using radio frequency transmitters, one for each fence, and one or more receivers, mounted at a location equidistant from the fences (Fig.7) and equipped with electricity and internet connection. Table 5 and 6 describes the specifications of transmitters and receivers. If a transmitter is reported to be malfunctioning, an inspection will be conducted within 24 hours after the event.

Fig. 7 – Control unit locations (red) and transmitters (green)

Table 5 – Control unit technical specifications

Control unit technical specifications	
Range with basic antenna	until to 10 km (*)
External antenna with extension cable	2.5 m o 10 m
Range with external antenna	until to 30 km (*)
RF transmission frequency	869.525MHz – 22dBm
Power supply:	
Input:	100-240V AC – 50/60 Hz – 0.6 A
Outputs:	14.0 V DC – 1000 mA
Backup battery	9.6V – 800mAh – NimH
Electricity consumption max	300mA
Protection class	IP20
Antenna dimensions included (W x H x D)	340 x 157 x 34mm
Dimensions without antenna (W x H x D)	126 x 157 x 34mm
Antenna weight included	450.9 g
(*) The range may be influenced by local conditions and climate.	

Table 6 – Transmitter technical specifications

Transmitter technical specifications	
Range with basic antenna	until to 10 km (*)
External antenna with extension cable	2.5 m o 10 m
Range with external antenna	until to 30 km (*)
RF transmission frequency	869.525MHz – 22dBm
Power supply:	2 cells C-LR14 da 1,5V
Operating temperature	da -15 °C a +50 °C
Protection class	IP44
Antenna dimensions included (W x H x D)	7.8 x 39.5 x 5.2 cm
Dimensions without antenna (W x H x D)	7.8 x 15.1 x 5.2 cm
Antenna weight and batteries included	366.2 g
Antenna weight included without batteries	230 g
(*) The range may be influenced by local conditions and climate.	

Conclusions

The system designed in this way should guarantee the protection of the clearing for at least 5 years, excluding the winter season which is still protected due to the snow. Further long-term observations may possibly reveal critical issues not identified in this study.

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